

Appendix Supplementary Table 1.

Sensors and data of the reviewed studies

No	Reference	Location (L), Time(T), Setting (S), Design (D)	Sample size (N), age restriction structure (A), gender (G)	Environment domains (ED), sensors	Environment-related outcome variables	Health domains (HD), sensors	Health-related outcome variables	Statistical analysis	Supplementary data
1	Benita, et al. [1]	L= Singapore; T= 10 minutes; S= 700m walking route.	N=10; A=21-25; G=Female.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: Kestrel 5400 Sensor 2: Smartphone.	Data 1: air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and mean radiant temperature; Data 2: environmental noise; Contextual: POI data.	HD= Activity and Mental health; Sensor 3: Empatica 4; Sensor 2: Smartphone.	Data 3: skin temperature and Electrodermal activity (EDA); Data 2: GPS and speed.	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) classifier algorithms are MNL, RFC and SVM; 3) Geo-visualization ;	1)Pre- and post-questionnaires
2	Benita and Tunçer [2]	L=Singapore; T=10 minutes;	N=10; A=21/25; G= Female.	ED= Physical and urban Environment Sensor 1: Kestrel 5400;	Data 1: Air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and	HD= Activity and Mental health; Sensor 3:	Data 3: Body skin temperature and Electrodermal activity (EDA).	1) Hierarchical clustering; 2) Stepwise regression, Ridge regression	1) Pro-Survey: Personal characteristics; 2) Post-survey: perceived

		S= 700m walking route.		Sensor 2: Smartphone	atmospheric pressure, Data 2: environmental noise. Contextual: Sky exposure in the city: 49 photographs were taken within about 10-15m distance;	Wrist-worn sensor Empatica 4. Sensor 2: Smartphone	Data 2: Geo-coordinates, and walking speed	(RR), Lasso regression (Lasso) and Random Forest (RF); 3) Pattern recognition tools and parametric tests to identify stress hotpots	Restorativeness : Hartig's Short-version Revised Perceived Restorativeness Scale (SRPRS) and Perceived Stress Scale (PSS))
3	Birenboim , et al. [3]	L= Utrecht ,Netherlands; T= 30 minutes; S= 3km walking route.	N=15(12); A= 21.8; G= Male.	ED= Urban Environment No particular sensor Geographic information system (GIS) environment.	Subjective data : survey to environment: Complete a questionnaire to rank ("1" most relaxing and "8" most stressful) Contextual: Predefined characteristics of the walking route segments	HD= Mental health; Sensor 1: GPS receiver; Sensor 2: Microsoft Band (MS Band); Sensor 3: Empatica E4.	Data 1: Geo-coordinates ; Data 2: Distance traveled, elevation, number of steps. Data 3: Heart Rate(HR), EDA, skin temperature	1) Geo-visualization ;	1) A third-party Android mobile application "Data Log" to log the measurements for Microsoft Band

4	Bohmer, et al. [4]	L= Rotterdam, Netherlands; T= 7-10 days S= Naturalistic.	N=82(48); A=50 years or older; G=Both.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: light sensor.	Data 1: Light exposure.	HD= Activity Sensor 2: accelerometer.	Data 2: Walk speed, bedtime.	1) Descriptive statistics;	1) Professional caregivers filled out questionnaires on the activities of daily living (ADL) and mobility of the participant.
5	Boissy, et al. [5]	L= Montreal, Canada; T= 14 days; S= Naturalistic.	N=75(54); A= 55–85 years of older; G=Both.	ED= Urban Environment No particular sensor.	Qualitative data: subjective survey about the proximity to neighbour services.	HD= Activity Sensor 1: GPS receiver; Sensor 2: A 3-axis accelerometer.	Data 1: Geo-coordinates; Data 2: Acceleration .	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) detection algorithm.	1) A performance evaluation and self-report questionnaire
6	Bolliger, et al. [6]	L= Ghent, Belgium; T= 15 days; S= Naturalistic;	N=5 (real-world); A=Adult; G=Both.	ED= Social Environment Sensor 1: Smartphone sensor.	Data 1: Applications, Barometer, Bluetooth, Light, Location, GPS, Screen, Temperature and voice activity , etc.	HD= Mental health and psychology Sensor 2: Empatica wristband; Sensor 1: Smartphone with the STRAW App.	Data 2: Physiological Data; Data 1: Ecological Momentary Assessment.	No particular analysis.	1) Online survey (demographics, work- and health-related information) ; 2) blood pressure and heart rate measurement

									during briefing; 3) personalized feedback report based on their own study results
7	Borghi, et al. [7]	L= Milan, Italy; T= 14 days (repeat in two seasons); S= Predefined (90km home-to-work route);	N=1: A=Adult; G= Not mentioned.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: DiSCmini; Sensor 2 : PM _{2.5} monitor Sensor 3: CairClip NO ₂ .	Data 1: UFP exposure Data 2: PM _{2.5} concentrations Data 3: NO ₂ concentrations	HD= Physical health; Sensor 4: Heart rate monitor.	Data 4: Heart rate and geo-coordinates.	1) Descriptive Analysis	
8	Burgi, et al. [8]	L= Zurich ,Switzerland; T= A week;	N=123(119) ; A=11-14; G=Both.	ED= urban environment No particular sensor	Contextual: Geospatial data (land use data, street network and points-of-interest);	HD= Activity Sensor 1: A GPS receiver. Sensor 2:	Data 1: Geo-coordinates; Data 2: short, intermittent bursts	1) Descriptive statistics	1) Complete a diary;

		S= Naturalistic;				Accelerometer	of activity		
9	Butt, et al. [9]	L= Cambridge, USA; T=Two weeks; S= Naturalistic;	N=20 (11); A=24/35; G=Both.	ED=Social environment Sensor 1: Smartphone augmented with "FunF sensing platform".	Data 1: Sensed and recorded proximity to nearby phones, implying people nearby.	HD= Activity Sensor 2: Wireless system (ZEO).	Data 2: Total sleep time(TST), rapid eye movement (REM), time in non-slow-wave NREM (light NREM), sleep and wake time, time taken to fall asleep.	1) Spearman's rank correlations; 2) Principal component analysis; 3) Wilcoxon sign-ranked test.	
10	Cerin, et al. [10]	L= Texas, USA; T= A week; S= Naturalistic;	N=84 (73/66); A= 3/5children and their parents; G=Both.	ED= urban environment No particular sensor	Qualitative data: Perceived traffic safety, traffic hazards, Perceived signs of physical and social disorder.	HD= Activity Sensor 1: GPS receiver. Sensor 2: Accelerometers.	Data 1: Geo-coordinates; Data 2: Physical activity (PA) and reducing sedentary behavior (SB).	1) Generalized additive mixed models (GAMMs).	1) Parents completed a survey:
11	Chaix, et al. [11]	L=Paris, France;	N=319(285);	ED= urban environment	Qualitative data:	HD= Activity	Data 1:	1) Descriptive statistics	

		T= A week; S= Naturalistic;	A= Average 50.2; G=Both.	No particular sensor	Questionnaire assessment of transport (Studies of residential characteristics and qualitative outcomes on mode choice).	Sensor 1: GPS receiver, TripBuilder Web mapping application Sensor 2: Accelerometers.	Geo-coordinates. Data 2: Physical activity (PA). Activity data: Phone-administered web mobility survey		
12	Chrisinger and King [12]	L= San Francisco, USA; T=20-25mins; S= Walking route;	N=14; A= - G=Both.	ED= Social and urban environment Device 1: Smartphone/tablet-based application, Discovery Tool (DT).	Data 1: Photos and audio narratives about elements of the built environment that contributed to or detracted from their well-being.	HD= Mental health; Sensor 1: Smartphone based GPS; Sensor 2: Empatica E4.	Data 1: Geo-coordinates; Data 1: Skin temperature, blood volume pressure, heart rate, heartbeat interval, and electrodermal activity (EDA).	1) Geo-visualization ; 2) Linear mixed model.	1) DT app allow people to describe aspects of this neighborhood environment that they felt influenced their well-being or the functioning of these public spaces.

13	Dessimon d, et al. [13]	L=Paris, France; T= 6.5 or 8 days ; S= Naturalistic;	N=1; A= Adult; G=Not mentioned.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: Canarin.	Data 1: real-time exposure to air pollutant; Contextual: POI data.	HD= Activity Sensor 2: tablet GPS.	Data 2: GPS trajectories. Activity diary	1) Descriptive Analysis; 2) Geo-visualization.	1) online survey
14	Do, et al. [14]	L= Southern California, USA; T= 7 days ; S= Naturalistic;	N=18; A= Adult; G=Both.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: PM monitor Sensor 2: Temperature logger	Data 1: Air pollutant PM2.5, PM10 concentration; Data 2: relative humidity (RH) and temperature. Contextual: Co-locate the personal monitors at the air monitoring site	HD= Activity Sensor 3: GPS data loggers. Extra: Wi-Fi hotpot	Data 3: Geo-coordinates.	1) Descriptive Analysis;	
15	Doherty and Oh [15]	L= Toronto, Canada; T=72h;	N=40(37); A=32/75; G=Both.	ED= urban environment No particular sensor.	Qualitative data: Subjective assessment	HD= Activity and physical health Sensor 1:	Data 1: Geo-coordinates; Data 2:	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) Geo-visualization.	1) A food/medicine diary and prompted

		S= Naturalistic;			from recall diary;	GPS receiver Sensor 2: Electrocardiogram (ECG) Sensor 3: Glucose monitoring A smartphone with custom software	Heart rate; Accelerometer; Data 3: Blood glucose. Activity data: Subjective data from recall diary.		recall activity diary; 2) Prompted recall activity diary, a Web-based interactive interface; 3) 2-h interview; 4) A follow-up survey asking subjects about their experience.
16	Donaire-Gonzalez, et al. [16]	L= five cities (Amsterdam and Utrecht-the Netherlands, Basel-Switzerland, Norwich-UK, and Torino-Italy);	N=158; A= Average 61 years old G= Both.	ED= Physical environment Sensor 1: MicroAeth Sensor 2 DiSCmini.	Data 1: Black carbon. Data 2: UFP number concentration. Contextual data: Green spaces from Open Street Map;	HD= Activity Sensor 3 Application "ExpoApp"; Sensor 4 GPS-Tracker; Sensor 5 Accelerometer.	Data 3: Geo-coordinates and accelerometer; Data 4 and Data 5 for testing; Activity data: Completed a TAD	1) Descriptive statistics.	1) Expo App can integrate and post-process data from portable sensors.

		Y=Three times for 24h in three seasons over one year S= Naturalistic;					(travel and activity diary		
17	Doryab, et al. [17]	L= Los Angeles, USA; T=16 weeks(one semester); S= Naturalistic;	N=188 (160); A= College student; G=Both.	ED= Social environment Sensor 1: Smartphone APP(AWARE).	Data 1: Nearby Bluetooth addresses, Wi-Fi, location, GPS, phone usage (when the screen status changed to on or off and locked or unlocked), and call and short message service (SMS) text messaging logs.	HD= Activity Sensor 2: A Fitbit Flex 2	Data 2: The number of steps taken and sleep status (asleep, awake, restless)	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) Aprior, frequent itemset algorithm for discovering associations among items; 3) Machine Learning Analysis.	1) Web-based questionnaires for an initial assessment of their health and well-being; 2) Post measurements .

18	El Aarbaoui and Chaix [18]	L=Paris, France; T= 7 days ; S= Naturalistic;	N=78(75); A= 34-74; G=Both.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: Personal Dosimeter.	Data 1: The sound level.	HD= Activity and physical health; Sensor 2: GPS receiver; Sensor 3: Actigraph accelerometer. Sensor 4: BioPatch BHM 3 Sensor;	Data 2: Geo-coordinates; Data 3: Accelerometer. Data 4: The HRV/HR	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) Linear-mixed models.	1) Phone Mobility survey
19	Engelniederhammer, et al. [19]	L= Hongkong, China; T= Mid-noon; S= Walking route with 4 street paths;	N=30; A= average 24.77 years old G=Both	ED=Social environment Sensor 1: Panasonic (NaPiOn) with infrared motion sensor;	Data 1: Human presence in an ambient space of up to 2 m distance.	HD= Mental health and psychology Sensor 2: GPS antenna. Sensor 3: Wristband: body monitor	Data 2: Geo-coordinates. Data 3: Skin conductivity and skin temperature .	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) logit models;	App questionnaire.
20	Huck, et al. [20]	L= Lancashire, UK	N=1; A= 28	ED=Physical environment	Data 1: Ambient NO2 concentration.	HD= Physical health	Data 2: Geo-coordinates;	1) Geo-visualization.	1)Data integrated in a Smartphone

		T= days S= A number of different routes, days and times around the city;	G= Male	Sensor 1: 2) NO2 sensor 'MiCS-2710'.		Sensor 2: 1) Smartphone-based GPS; Sensor 3: 'Airflow Sensor'.	Data 3: The frequency and relative depth of breathing with the timestamps.		software 'Spatial Logger'.
21	Johnston, et al. [21]	L= Southern California, USA; T= average of 18 h per participant; S= Naturalistic;	N=18(10); A= Youth (15-17); G=Both.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: Personal PM2.5 monitor Sensor 2: Phone	Data 1: PM2.5 concentrations Data 2: temperature, and relative humidity	HD= Psychology; Sensor 2: Smartphone-based GPS.	Data 2: Geo-coordinates; Psychology: Photographs , videos to document what they saw.	No particular analysis.	1) Popular Education Workshops to cover a broad overview of air pollution. 2) discussion about the questions or ideas.
22	Kanjo, et al. [22]	L= Nottingham, UK; T= 45mins	N=40; A=28; G=Female.	ED=Physical environment Sensor 1: Smartphone;	Data 1: Noise; Data 2: Air pressure Light (UV).	HD= Mental health & Psychology Sensor 1: Smartphone;	Data 1: Geo-coordinates; Data 2:	1) Principle Component Analysis (PCA);	

		S= Shopping route;		Sensor 2: Microsoft band		Sensor 2: Microsoft band.	1) Heart Rate (HR), 2) Electro Dermal Activities (EDA) 3) Body Temperatur e 4) Hand Acceleration Self-Report of Emotion (1-5) from an App "EnvBodySe ns".	2)Multi- variant regression analysis;	
23	Kim, et al. [23]	L= Lincoln, Nebraska, USA; T= - S= 1.26 km walking route;	N=30; A= Average 24.2 years ago G=both.	ED= Urban environment No particular sensor.	Qualitative data: subjective assessment about walkability.	HD= Physical health and activity Sensor 1: Smartphone- based application; Sensor 2 Commercial IMU (Motion Studio) ;	Data 1: Geo- coordinates; Data 2: Acceleromet er; Data 3: 1) Heart rate, 2) Photoplethy	1) calculation of gait stability and acceleration; 3) Point biserial correlation coefficient (rpb)	1) additional explanation of the rating followed a walkability checklist.

						Sensor 3: Empatica E4.	smography (PPG); 3) Blood Volume Pulse (BVP);		
24	Kou, et al. [24]	L= Chicago, USA; T= a weekday and a weekend day; S= Naturalistic;	N=46(33); A=18-65; G=Both.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: portable sound sensor.	Data 1: Noise level	HD= Activity Sensor 2: GPS-equipped mobile phone.	Data 2: Geo-coordinates; Activity data: Activity diaries.	1) Descriptive analysis 2) Multilevel logistic regression analysis	1) Survey questionnaire that collected his/her demographic information and self-reported health status
25	Laeremans, et al. [25]	L= Antwerp, Belgium; Barcelona, Spain. London, UK; T=7 days, three times in different seasons;	N=122; A= Average 35 years old G= both.	ED= Physical environment Sensor 1: MicroAeth.	Data 1: AP exposure and level of Black Carbon.	HD= Physical health and activity Sensor 2: SenseWear armband.	Data 2: 1) Heat flux, 2) Galvanic skin response, skin temperature 3) Accelerometer.	1) Kenward-Roger's approximation;	1) At the end of each measurement week, conducting a battery of non-invasive measurements about HRV, retinal vessel diameters, FeNO, and lung function

		S= : Naturalist ic;							at a research center in each of the three cities
26	Ma, et al. [26]	L=Beijing, China; T= 48 hours (a workday and a weekend day); S= Naturalist ic;	N=117 (97) residents; A=18-60; G=Both.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: SLM-25 Sound Level Meters.	Data 1: real-time noise level	HD= Activity; Sensor 2: Smartphone based GPS	Data 2: Geo- coordinates; Activity data: Two-day activity- travel diary	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) Regression modeling; 3) 3D geo- visualization;	1) A questionnaire
27	Ma, et al. [27]	L=Beijing, China; T= 48 hours (a workday and a weekend day);	N=117(112) residents; A=18-60; G=Both.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: air pollutant sensors.	Data 1: Real-time PM2.5 concentration Contextual: Residence- based monitoring station assessment	HD= Activity; Sensor 2: GPS- equipped smartphone	Data 2: Geo- coordinates; Qualitative data: Self- reported mental health	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) 3D geo- visualization;	1) A questionnaire

		S= Naturalistic;					activity-travel diaries.		
28	Millar, et al. [28]	L=F261 cycle highway from Tilburg via Loon op Zand to Waalwijk, Netherlands; T= a day; S= 18km long between urban and rural;	N=12; A= half aged 18-24, the remaining half were older 55; G=Both.	ED= Urban Environment Sensor 1: Camera.	Data 1: Recording participants' view; Contextual: Digital surface model (DSM) and a land use map, three geospatial data sets.	HD= Mental health; Sensor 2: Smartphone GPS App; Sensor 3: Empatica E4.	Data 2: Geo-coordinates; Data 3: Heart Rate; Temperature, Skin conductivity .	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) Multilevel models; 3) Geo-visualization.	
29	Novak, et al. [29]	L= Ljubljana, Slovenia; T= 7 days; S= Naturalistic;	N=2; A=Adult; G=-.	ED= Physical Environment Sensor 1: PM measuring unit.	Data 1: real-time PM2.5, PM10 concentration.	HD= Physical health; Sensor 2: Activity tracker (SAT).	Data 2: Hart rate.	1) Four models to approach the data; 2) Summary statistics.	Compared personal monitors with values obtained government run AQ station.

30	Ojha, et al. [30]	L= Zürich, Switzerland; T=- S= 1.3km walking route;	N=30; A= - G= -	ED= urban and physical environment Sensor 1: A sensor backpack.	Data 1: 1) Sound level 2) The amount of dust (mg/m ³), 3) Temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), and illuminance (lx). Contextual: Field-of-view based on the GPS information and spatial configuration of the neighborhood by photo.	HD= Mental health; Sensor 2: GPS receiver Sensor3: Wrist-worn sensor Empatica E4.	Data 2: GPS location Data 3: Biological signal Electrodermal activity (EDA).	1) REP-Tree (a decision tree) to build a predictive model; 2) ten-fold cross-validation to validate; 3) FURIA a fuzzy rule-based classifier to build inferential modeling; 4) Backward feature elimination (BFE) method to abstract feature; 5) Self-organizing map (SOM).	
31	Rabinovich, et al. [31]	L= Morgridge, USA;	N=30;	ED= Physical environment	Data 1:	HD= Physical health;	Data 3: Geo-coordinates;	1) Linear mixed models.	1) Samples were batch

		T=4 school days; twice in two non-consecutive weeks S= : Naturalistic;	A= schoolchildren average 10 years old; G=-	Sensor 1: Aerosol nephelometer; Sensor 2: Temperature sensor.	PM concentrations ; Data 2: Ambient temperature.	Sensor 3: GPS receiver; Device: Monitor Doser.	health data: School-time albuterol use as the total number of activations.		assayed for uLTE4. 2) Daily surveys included questions determining presence or absence of upper respiratory infection.
32	Resch, et al. [32]	L= Salzburg, Austria; Cologne, Germany T= Within a day; S= Naturalistic;	N=56; A=over 18; G=Both.	ED= Urban Environment Sensor 1: GoPro camera.	Data 1: First-person video camera.	HD= Mental health and psychology; Sensor 2: Smartphone-based eDiary app. Sensor 3: Empatica 4; Sensor 4: Zephyr Bioharness;	Data 2: Geo-location Data 3: GSR and ST; Data 4: Cardiological parameters like ECG, HRV, and others;	1) Visual analytics; 2) Descriptive analysis;	A geo-located (post-hoc paper-pencil) questionnaire.
33	Roe, et al. [33]	L= Virginia, USA;	N=11; A= age 65; G=Both.	ED= Physical Environment; Sensor 1:	Data 1: Noise (dB); Data 2: Air quality.	HD=Physical health, mental health and psychology	Data 3: GPS data and accelerometer;	1) Descriptive analysis;	1) Pre- and Post-walk assessment

		T= Unassisted walking for 15–20 min; S= Naturalistic;		Noise sensors ; Sensor 2: Airbeam sensors.		Sensor 3: Phone app Sensor 4: Smart watch	Data 4: Heart rate variability; Walking speed Self-report: Mood and Subjective well-being;	2) Linear mixed effects models.	
34	Runkle, et al. [34]	L= three sites: Starkville, Boone and Raleigh, United States; Y=5 days; S= : Naturalistic; D= Longitudinal.	N=66 (35); A=16-35; G= both.	ED= Physical environment Sensor 1: ThermoChron iButton;	Data 1 (n=66): Direct exposure to ambient temperature.	HD= Physical health Sensor 2: Garmin smartwatch	Data 2: Geo-coordinates; Heart rate and collect physiologic monitoring data.	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) Quasi-Poisson regression.	1) a heat illness survey, 2) time activity logs to capture changes in work activity;
35	Rybarczyk, et al. [35]	L= Wuppertal, Germany;	N=28; A= 20-70; G=Both.	HD= Urban Environment; Sensor 1:	Qualitative data: Roadway conditions	HD= Physical health and activity; Sensor 2:	Data 2: GPS location Data 3:	1) Descriptive statistics;	1) a short survey,

		T= hours; S= Naturalistic; within 1.1 km ² ;		GoPro Hero 3 and 4	Contextual: Land-use types, road type, road speed limit and roadway width, tree density, Bicycle facility type.	tablet-based GPS; Sensor 3: Garmin VÍvoSmart;	heart rate, altimeter, accelerometer.	3) Linear regression model and spatial auto-regression.	
	Shoval, <i>et al.</i> [36]	L= Jerusalem, Israel; T= A day; S= Naturalistic settings;	N=144 (68); A= over 18 G= both.	ED=Urban environment No particular sensor.	Qualitative data: location-triggered surveys.	HD= Mental health And psychology Sensor 1: Smartphone GPS; Sensor 2: Wrist-worn sensor Empatica E4; Sensor 3: Smartphone application, 'Sensometer'.	Data1: Geo-coordinates; Data 2(n=68) Skin conductance , heart rate measures, blood pressure, and skin temperature ; Emotion data: time-triggered surveys.	1) Geo-visualization; 2) Descriptive statistics.	

37	Steinle, <i>et al.</i> [37]	L= Edinburgh, Scotland; T= Days in winter and summer; S= Naturalistic settings;	N=17; A=- G=-	ED= Physical environments Sensor 1: Dylos DC 1700;	Data1: Particle number counts (PNC); Contextual: Time-activity diaries (TADs) and questions about building and neighbor characteristics.	HD= Activity Sensor 2: GPS receiver	Data 2: Geo-coordinates; Activity data: Web-based Time-activity diaries (TADs);	1) visualization of data. 2) Descriptive statistics.	1) Follow-up meeting, a web-form questionnaire ;
38	West, <i>et al.</i> [38]	L= Nairobi, Kenya; T= two weeks; S= Naturalistic; D= Longitudinal.	N=6; A= 18-55; G=Both.	HD= Physical Environment; Sensor 1: Dylos 1700.	Data 1: PM concentrations ; Contextual: Assessment from Mobile Air Pollution Laboratory.	HD= Psychology; Sensor 2: GPS tracker;	Data 2: GPS trajectories; Perception data: questionnaire.	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) visualization of data.	1) workshops to discuss citizen science and potential actions. 2) Pre- and Post-questionnaire
39	Zhang, <i>et al.</i> [39]	L=Guangzhou, China;	N=156(138) ; A=over 18;	ED= Physical and social Environment Sensor 1:	Data 1: SLM-25 Sound Level Meters;	HD= Psychology;	Data 4: GPS trajectories; EMA data:	1) Descriptive statistics; 2) Hierarchical logistic	1) Daily activity and environmental health

		<p>T= a weekday and a weekend day;</p> <p>S= Naturalistic;</p>	G=Both.	<p>Noise sensors ;</p> <p>Sensor 2: Air sensors;</p> <p>Sensor 3: Mobile signal detection</p>	<p>Data 2: Real-time PM2.5, temperature and humidity</p> <p>Data3: Number of mobile phones in the surrounding</p>	Sensor 4: GPS-equipped mobile phones	<p>Geographic eco-logical momentary assessment (GEMA) of environmental perceptions and emotions.</p>	<p>logistic models (HLMs)</p>	<p>questionnaire survey;</p>
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Appendix Supplementary Table 2. Checklist for the methodological quality assessment

Criteria1	Description	Score
Study purpose	Was the purpose and/or research question stated clearly?	
	No	0
	Yes	1
Literature	Was relevant background literature reviewed?	
	No	0
	Yes	1
Sampling	Was the process of purposeful selection described?	
	No	0
	Yes (e.g. probability sampling methods were used)	1
	Are the individuals selected to participate in the study likely to be representative of the target population? / was sample size justified?	
	Weak	0
	Moderate	1
	Strong	2
	Was informed consent obtained?	
	No	0
	Yes	1
Study Design2	Cross-sectional study 1 (Minutes/ Hours within a day)	0
	Cross-sectional study 2 (Days / Weeks)	1
	Longitudinal study (Months and Seasons)	2
Data Collection Method	Clear & complete description about site and participants	
	No	0
	Yes	1
	Was the measurement tool used valid and reliable (humans' responses)?	
	Weak	0
Moderate	1	

¹ The checklist was adapted from previously established assessment tools (EPHPP,2010; Law al.,1998), this adaption was used by Won et al (2016).

² This review focuses on the measurement of environment and health in the fieldwork, rather than medical research in lab, so we use the criteria of Study design adapted by Won et al (2016).

	Strong	2
	Was the measurement tool used valid and reliable (environment independent variable)?	
	Weak	0
	Moderate	1
	Strong	2
Withdrawals	Were drop-outs/exclusion reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	
	No	0
	Yes	1
Confounders	Were relevant confounders controlled?	
	Weak	0
	Moderate	1
	Strong	2
Data Analysis	Were the statistical methods appropriate for the study design?	
	Weak	0
	Moderate	1
	Strong	2
	Was the process of analysing data described adequately?	
	No	0
	Yes	1
Conclusion & Implications	Were conclusions appropriate given the study findings?	
	No	0
	Yes	1

Appendix Supplementary Table 3.

Quality assessment of the reviewed studies.

MT-Human: measurement tool used for human (0-No; 1- Traditional & subjective data; 2- Objective measurement such as GPS, accelerometer, health tracker)

DD-Human: Data dimension of objectively measuring humans' responses (0- Low-dimensions; 1- High- dimensions)

MT- Environment: measurement tool used for Environment (0-No; 1- Traditional & subjective data; 2- Objective measurement such as personalized environmental sensors)

DD- Environment: Data dimension of objectively measuring environment (0- Low-dimensions; 1- High- dimensions)

No.	RE	Purpose	Literature	Sampling			Study design	Data collection			Withdrawals	Confounders	Data Analysis		Conclusion	Total Score
				Purpose	representation	Consent		Description	Health	environment			Method	Processes		
1	Benita, et al. [1]	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	2	2	0	2	2	1	1	15(M)
2	Benita and Tunçer [2]	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	2	2	0	2	2	1	1	15(M)
3	Birenboim, et al. [3]	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	2	1	1	2	0	1	1	12(M)
4	Bohmer, et al. [4]	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	0	1	1	16(H)
5	Boissy, et al. [5]	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	16(H)
6	Bolliger, et al. [6]	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	11(L)
7	Borghini, et al. [7]	1	1	0	0	0	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	1	0	10(L)
8	Burgi, et al. [8]	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	15(M)
9	Butt, et al. [9]	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	2	2	1	0	2	1	1	15(M)

10	Cerin, et al. [10]	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	17(H)
11	Chaix, et al. [11]	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	15(M)
12	Chrisinger and King [12]	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	12(M)
13	Dessimond, et al. [13]	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	1	10(L)
14	Do, et al. [14]	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	0	1	0	1	1	9(L)
15	Doherty and Oh [15]	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	12(M)
16	Donaire-Gonzalez, et al. [16]	1	1	0	2	1	2	1	2	2	0	1	0	1	1	15(M)
17	Doryab, et al. [17]	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	19(H)
18	El Aarbaoui and Chaix [18]	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	17(H)
19	Engelniederhammer, et al. [19]	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	2	2	0	1	1	1	1	13(M)
20	Huck, et al. [20]	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	1	1	10(L)
21	Johnston, et al. [21]	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	2	1	0	0	0	1	8(L)
22	Kanjo, et al. [22]	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	2	2	0	2	2	1	1	16(H)
23	Kim, et al. [23]	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	2	1	1	1	12(M)
24	Kou, et al. [24]	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	15(M)

25	Laeremans, et al. [25]	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	0	2	1	1	1	18(H)
26	Ma, et al. [26]	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	16(H)
27	Ma, et al. [27]	1	1	0	2	0	1	1	1	2	1	1	0	1	1	13(M)
28	Millar, et al. [28]	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	2	2	0	1	1	1	1	12(M)
29	Novak, et al. [29]	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	2	2	0	0	2	1	1	12(M)
30	Ojha, et al. [30]	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	2	2	0	1	2	1	1	13(M)
31	Rabinovitch, et al. [31]	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	0	1	1	1	1	14(M)
32	Resch, et al. [32]	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	2	2	0	1	1	1	1	13(M)
33	Roe, et al. [33]	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	2	2	0	2	1	1	1	14(M)
34	Runkle, et al. [34]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	17(H)
35	Rybarczyk, et al. [35]	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	2	2	0	1	2	1	1	14(M)
36	Shoval, et al. [36]	1	1	1	2	1	0	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	14(M)
37	Steinle, et al. [37]	1	1	0	0	0	2	1	1	2	0	1	0	1	1	11(L)
38	West, et al. [38]	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	1	11(L)
39	Zhang, et al. [39]	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	16(H)

Appendix Supplementary Table 4

Sensors and devices in the reviewed studies

Topic	Sensor		Index	Reference
Health tracker to monitor human responses	Wristband	Empatica (E4) ³	Body skin temperature and Electrodermal activity (EDA), etc.	Benita, et al. [1] Benita and Tunçer [2] Bolliger, et al. [6] Chrisinger and King [12] Kim, et al. [23] Millar, <i>et al.</i> [28] Ojha, et al. [30] Resch, et al. [32] Shoval, <i>et al.</i> [36].
		Microsoft Band ⁴ (MS Band)	Heart rate (HR), Electrodermal activity (EDA), skin temperature, blood volume pulse (BVP), etc.	Birenboim, <i>et al.</i> [3] Kanjo, et al. [22].
		A Fitbit Flex ⁵ (Fitbit)	The number of steps taken and sleep status (asleep, awake, restless), etc.	Doryab, et al. [17]
		Garmin ⁶	Heart rate (HR), steps, etc.	Novak, <i>et al.</i> [29] Runkle, et al. [34] Rybarczyk, <i>et al.</i> [35].
		Heart rate monitor (Suunto 9 ⁷)	Heart beat (HB), etc.	Borghi, et al. [7] Rybarczyk, <i>et al.</i> [35].
		Body monitor wristband	Skin conductivity and skin temperature, etc.	Engelniederhammer, et al. [19].
		Huawei watch	Photoplethysmogram (PPG)	Roe, et al. [33].
	Armband	SenseWear ⁸	Heat flux, galvanic skin response, skin temperature, etc.	Laeremans, et al. [25].
Chest Strap	BioPatch BHM 3	Electrocardiogram (ECG) signal	El Aarbaoui and Chaix [18].	

³ Empatica, more information: <https://www.empatica.com/en-int/>;

⁴ Microsoft Band, more information: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Microsoft_Band

⁵ Fibit, more information: <https://www.fitbit.com/global/dk/home>;

⁶ Garmin, more information: <https://www.garmin.com/en-US/>;

⁷ Suunto 9, more information: <https://www.suunto.com/da-dk/suunto-collections/suunto-9-collection/>

⁸ SenseWear, more information: <chrome-extension://ohfgljdgelakfkefopgkclcohadegdpjf/http://nutrizionista-gorizia.it/resources/MicroStar---Rheo-Scan---D-300.pdf>;

		Zephyr Bioharness ⁹	Electrocardiogram (ECG) signal	Resch, et al. [32].
	Other medical sensors	Alive Heart Monitor ¹⁰	Electrocardiogram (ECG) signal	Doherty and Oh [15].
		Glucose monitor (Medtronic ¹¹)	Blood glucose, etc.	Doherty and Oh [15].
		Airflow Sensor	The frequency and relative depth of breathing, etc.	Huck, et al. [20].
		Sleep monitor (ZEO12)	Total sleep time (TST), rapid eye movement (REM), etc.	Butt, et al. [9].
Motion	physical activity	Accelerometer	Acceleration, speed and direction, etc.	Bohmer, et al. [4] Burgi, et al. [8] Cerin, et al. [10] Chaix, et al. [11] Doherty and Oh [15] Donaire-Gonzalez, et al. [16] El Aarbaoui and Chaix [18] Kim, et al. [23] Laeremans, et al. [25].
Environment sensors to measure exposure		Wind sensor	Wind speed.	Benita and Tunçer [2]
		Air Pressure sensor	Atmospheric pressure, etc.	Benita, et al. [1] Benita and Tunçer [2] Kanjo, et al. [22]
		Light sensor	Illuminance, Light exposure etc.	Bohmer, et al. [4] Kanjo, et al. [22] Ojha, et al. [30]
		Sound sensor	Noise level, etc.	Benita, et al. [1] Benita and Tunçer [2] El Aarbaoui and Chaix [18] Johnston, et al. [21] Kou, et al. [24] Ma, et al. [26] Ojha, et al. [30] Roe, et al. [33] Zhang, et al. [39]
		Temperature sensor	Air temperature, relative humidity, etc.	Benita, et al. [1] Benita and Tunçer [2] Do, et al. [14] Ojha, et al. [30] Rabinovitch, et al. [31] Runkle, et al. [34]

⁹ Zephyr Bioharness, more information: <https://www.zephyranywhere.com/>

¹⁰ Alive Heart Monitor, more information: <https://www.kardia.com/>

¹¹ Medtronic, more information: <https://www.medtronicdiabetes.com/treatments/continuous-glucose-monitoring;>

¹² Zeo sleep tracking, more information: [https://polyphasic.net/sleep-tracking/zeo-sleep-tracking/;](https://polyphasic.net/sleep-tracking/zeo-sleep-tracking/)

		Dust sensor	The level of dust in the air	Ojha, et al. [30]
		Infrared motion sensor	Distance and Density, etc.	Engelniederhammer, et al. [19]
		camera	View, etc.	Millar, et al. [28] Resch, et al. [32] Rybarczyk, et al. [35].
		Nitrogen Dioxide (NO ₂) sensor	Ambient NO ₂ concentration, etc.	Borgh, et al. [7] Huck, et al. [20] Kanjo, et al. [22]
		Particulate Matter (PM)	The concentration of particulates number, such as PM1, PM2.5, PM10, etc.	Dessimond, et al. [13] Do, et al. [14] Donaire-Gonzalez, et al. [16] Johnston, et al. [21] Laeremans, et al. [25] Ma, et al. [27] Novak, et al. [29] Ojha, et al. [30] Rabinovitch, et al. [31] Roe, et al. [33] Steinle, et al. [37] West, et al. [38] Zhang, et al. [39]
		Ultrafine Particles (UFPs)	UFP exposure levels	Borgh, et al. [7] Donaire-Gonzalez, et al. [16]
		Black carbon monitor	Black carbon levels	Donaire-Gonzalez, et al. [16] Laeremans, et al. [25]
	GPS	GPS receiver	Geographic coordinates.	Birenboim, et al. [3] Boissy, et al. [5] Burgi, et al. [8] Cerin, et al. [10] Chaix, et al. [11] Do, et al. [14] Doherty and Oh [15] Donaire-Gonzalez, et al. [16] El Aarbaoui and Chaix [18] Engelniederhammer, et al. [19] Huck, et al. [20] Ojha, et al. [30] Rabinovitch, et al. [31] Runkle, et al. [34] Steinle, et al. [37] West, et al. [38]
Sensor-inbuilt GPS		Geographic coordinates.	Borgh, et al. [7]	

Smartphone based	Geo-coordinates	Position service.	Benita, <i>et al.</i> [1] Benita and Tunçer [2] Bolliger, <i>et al.</i> [6] Chaix, <i>et al.</i> [11] Chrisinger and King [12] Dessimond, <i>et al.</i> [13] Donaire-Gonzalez, <i>et al.</i> [16] Bolliger, <i>et al.</i> [6] Huck, <i>et al.</i> [20] Johnston, <i>et al.</i> [21] Kanjo, <i>et al.</i> [22] Kim, <i>et al.</i> [23] Kou, <i>et al.</i> [24] Ma, <i>et al.</i> [26] Ma, <i>et al.</i> [27] Millar, <i>et al.</i> [28] Resch, <i>et al.</i> [32] Roe, <i>et al.</i> [33] Shoval, <i>et al.</i> [36] Rybarczyk, <i>et al.</i> [35] Zhang, <i>et al.</i> [39]
	Accelerometer	Acceleration, speed and direction, etc.	Donaire-Gonzalez, <i>et al.</i> [16] Roe, <i>et al.</i> [33]
	Wifi	Location; network	Do, <i>et al.</i> [14]
	Light	Luminance of the ambient light	Bolliger, <i>et al.</i> [6]
	Microphone	Voice activity; noise	Benita, <i>et al.</i> [1] Benita and Tunçer [2] Bolliger, <i>et al.</i> [6] Kanjo, <i>et al.</i> [22]
	Bluetooth	Proximity; Social communication	Bolliger, <i>et al.</i> [6] Doryab, <i>et al.</i> [17]
	Images	Narratives and views.	Chrisinger and King [12]
	Temperature	Temperature of the phone's hardware sensor	Bolliger, <i>et al.</i> [6] Johnston, <i>et al.</i> [21]
	Application	Such as "FunF sensing platform", "ExpoApp", "eDiary", "Aware", "Sensometer", etc.	Butt, <i>et al.</i> [9] Chrisinger and King [12] Donaire-Gonzalez, <i>et al.</i> [16] Doryab, <i>et al.</i> [17] Kim, <i>et al.</i> [23] Shoval, <i>et al.</i> [36] Resch, <i>et al.</i> [32]

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